

**THE LOG-BEHAVIOR OF SOME SEQUENCES RELATED TO A
LINEAR RECURRENCE SEQUENCE**

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Abstract

Let $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence satisfying the recurrence relation

$$(n+1)A_{n+1} = 2(n+1)A_n + 3(n-1)A_{n-1},$$

with the initial conditions $A_0 = 1$ and $A_1 = 1$. Let Δ be the (forward) difference operator. In this paper, we are interested in the log-behavior of some sequences involving A_n . We mainly show that $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ and $\{\Delta^3 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ are log-balanced. In addition, we prove that some sequences such as $\{nA_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{\Delta(nA_n)\}_{n \geq 1}$, and $\{n \cdot \Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ are log-concave.

1. Introduction

Let $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence satisfying the recurrence relation

$$(n+1)A_{n+1} = 2(n+1)A_n + 3(n-1)A_{n-1}, \tag{1}$$

with the initial conditions $A_0 = 1$ and $A_1 = 1$. The sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is sequence A005773 in the OEIS [9] and $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ appeared in Exercise 6.46 of Stanley [11]. The value of A_n is equal to the number of symmetric Dyck paths of semilength $2n-1$ with no peaks at even level. For more properties of $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, see sequence A005773 in the OEIS [9]. Some sequences involving A_n play an important role in combinatorial enumeration problems. Let Δ be the (forward) difference operator. The first difference sequence of $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is $\{\Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 0} = \{A_{n+1} - A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ and $\{\Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is related to sequence A025566 in the OEIS [9]. Let $\{a_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ denote sequence A025566 in the OEIS [9]. The value of a_{n+1} is the number of Motzkin $(2n)$ -paths whose last weak valley occurs immediately after step n . For the definition of the weak valley and more properties of $\{a_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, see sequence A025566 in the

OEIS [9]. For $n \geq 2$, $a_n = \Delta A_{n-1} = A_n - A_{n-1}$. The second difference sequence of $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is

$$\Delta^2 A_n = \Delta(\Delta A_n) = \Delta(A_{n+1} - A_n) = A_{n+2} - 2A_{n+1} + A_n.$$

The sequence $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is sequence A026135 in the OEIS [9] and the value of $\Delta^2 A_n$ is the total number of rows of consecutive peaks in all Motzkin $(n+2)$ -paths. The sequence $\{nA_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is sequence A132894 in the OEIS [9] and the value of nA_n is the number of peaks in all paths of length $n+1$ with steps $U = (1, 1)$, $D = (1, -1)$, and $H = (1, 0)$, which start at $(0, 0)$ and stay weakly above the x -axis. Hence the properties of sequences related to A_n deserve to be studied.

The main purpose of this paper is to investigate the log-behavior of some sequences involving A_n . Now we recall some definitions that we will need in this paper. A positive sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is called *log-convex* (*log-concave*) if $z_n^2 \leq z_{n-1}z_{n+1}$ ($z_n^2 \geq z_{n-1}z_{n+1}$) for each $n \geq 1$. A log-convex sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is called *log-balanced* if $\{\frac{z_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-concave (Došlić [3] gave this definition). It is clear that a sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-convex (log-concave) if and only if its quotient sequence $\{\frac{z_{n+1}}{z_n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is nondecreasing (nonincreasing) and a log-convex sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-balanced if and only if $\{\frac{z_{n+1}}{(n+1)z_n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is nonincreasing. Log-convexity (Log-concavity) is a fertile source of combinatorial inequalities and plays an important role in many subjects (see for instance [1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10]). In this paper, we are interested in the log-behavior of some sequences involving A_n . For instance, we show that $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ and $\{\Delta^3 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ are log-balanced, $\{nA_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is log-concave, and $\{n^n A_n^n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is log-convex.

2. Main Results

We first give a lemma.

Lemma 1. *For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), let $x_n = \frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n}$ ($n \geq 0$). For $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$x_n \leq \varphi_n, \tag{2}$$

and

$$\frac{x_{n+1}}{x_n} \geq \frac{2(3n^2 + 6n + 2)}{(n+2)(2n+1)\varphi_n}, \tag{3}$$

where $\varphi_n = \frac{3(2n+1)}{2(n+1)}$.

Proof. By using (1), we get

$$x_n = 2 + \frac{3(n-1)}{(n+1)x_{n-1}} \quad \text{for } n \geq 1. \tag{4}$$

We prove by induction that (2) holds. It is clear that $x_j \leq \varphi_j$ for $0 \leq j \leq 3$. Assume that $x_k \leq \varphi_k$ for $k \geq 3$. It follows from (4) that

$$x_{k+1} - \varphi_{k+1} = 2 + \frac{3k}{(k+2)x_k} - \varphi_{k+1}.$$

Since Liu and Wang [7] proved that

$$x_n \geq \mu_n \quad \text{for } n \geq 0, \tag{5}$$

where $\mu_n = \frac{6n}{2n+1}$, it follows from (5) that

$$x_{k+1} - \varphi_{k+1} \leq 2 + \frac{3k}{(k+2)\mu_k} - \varphi_{k+1} = 2 + \frac{2k+1}{2(k+2)} - \frac{3(2k+3)}{2(k+2)} = 0.$$

Thus $x_n \leq \varphi_n$ for $n \geq 0$. It follows from (2) and (4) that

$$\frac{x_{n+1}}{x_n} \geq \frac{2}{\varphi_n} + \frac{3n}{(n+2)\varphi_n^2} = \frac{2(3n^2 + 6n + 2)}{(n+2)(2n+1)\varphi_n}.$$

□

For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), Liu and Wang [7] proved that $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-convex, and Zhao [12] showed that $\{A_{n+1} - A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-convex. Now we discuss the log-behavior of some sequences involving A_n such as $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, $\{\Delta^3 A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, and $\{nA_n\}_{n \geq 1}$.

Theorem 1. *For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), the sequences $\{\Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ and $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ are log-balanced.*

Proof. For $n \geq 0$, put $x_n = \frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n}$, $\bar{x}_n = \frac{A_{n+2} - A_{n+1}}{(n+1)(A_{n+1} - A_n)}$ ($n \geq 1$), and $y_n = \frac{\Delta^2 A_{n+1}}{\Delta^2 A_n}$. It is clear that $\bar{x}_n = \frac{x_n(x_{n+1} - 1)}{(n+1)(x_n - 1)}$. It follows from (1) that

$$\Delta^2 A_n = \frac{2(2n+1)}{n+2} A_n \quad \text{for } n \geq 0. \tag{6}$$

The values of $\{\Delta^2 A_j\}_{0 \leq j \leq 10}$ are

1, 2, 5, 14, 39, 110, 312, 890, 2550, 7334, 21161, 61226, 177575.

By applying (4), we derive

$$\bar{x}_n = \frac{x_n}{(n+1)(x_n - 1)} + \frac{3n}{(n+1)(n+2)(x_n - 1)} \quad (n \geq 1).$$

Since the two sequences $\{\frac{x_n}{(n+1)(x_n - 1)}\}_{n \geq 1}$ and $\{\frac{n}{(n+1)(n+2)(x_n - 1)}\}_{n \geq 2}$ are decreasing, it follows that $\{\bar{x}_n\}_{n \geq 2}$ is decreasing. We have that $\{\frac{A_{n+1} - A_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 2}$ is log-concave. Note that Zhao [12] showed that $\{A_{n+1} - A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-convex, and

hence $\{\Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-balanced. In order to prove that the sequence $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-convex, we need to show that $\{y_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is increasing. By means of (6), we get

$$y_n = \frac{(n+2)(2n+3)}{(n+3)(2n+1)}x_n \quad \text{for } n \geq 0. \tag{7}$$

It follows from (7) that

$$\begin{aligned} y_{n+1} - y_n &= \frac{(n+3)(2n+5)}{(n+4)(2n+3)}x_{n+1} - \frac{(n+2)(2n+3)}{(n+3)(2n+1)}x_n \\ &= \frac{(n+3)^2(2n+1)(2n+5)x_{n+1} - (n+2)(n+4)(2n+3)^2x_n}{(n+3)(n+4)(2n+1)(2n+3)}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows from (4) that

$$\begin{aligned} &(n+3)^2(2n+1)(2n+5)x_{n+1} - (n+2)(n+4)(2n+3)^2x_n \\ &= (n+3)^2(2n+1)(2n+5) \left[2 + \frac{3n}{(n+2)x_n} \right] - (n+2)(n+4)(2n+3)^2x_n. \end{aligned}$$

By using (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} &(n+3)^2(2n+1)(2n+5)x_{n+1} - (n+2)(n+4)(2n+3)^2x_n \\ &\geq (n+3)^2(2n+1)(2n+5) \left[2 + \frac{3n}{(n+2)\varphi_n} \right] - (n+2)(n+4)(2n+3)^2\varphi_n \\ &= 2(n+3)^2(2n+1)(2n+5) + 2n(n+1)(n+3)^2 \left(2 + \frac{1}{n+2} \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{3(n+2)(n+4)(2n+1)(2n+3)^2}{2(n+1)} \\ &= 5n^2 - 10n - 30 + \frac{2n(n+1)}{n+2} + \frac{3(n+2)(n+4)}{2(n+1)} > 0 \quad (n \geq 3). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\{y_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is increasing. By (4), we have

$$\frac{x_n}{n+1} = \frac{2}{n+1} + \frac{3(n-1)}{(n+1)^2x_{n-1}} \quad \text{for } n \geq 1.$$

Since $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is increasing and $\{\frac{n-1}{(n+1)^2}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is decreasing, it follows that the sequence $\{\frac{x_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is decreasing. Noting that

$$\frac{y_n}{n+1} = \left(1 + \frac{3}{2n^2 + 7n + 3} \right) \frac{x_n}{n+1},$$

we have that $\{\frac{y_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is decreasing. This indicates that $\{\frac{\Delta^2 A_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-concave, and hence $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-balanced. \square

n	Δb_n
0	1
1	3
2	9
3	25
4	71
5	202
6	578
7	1660
8	4784
9	13827
10	40065
11	116349
12	338539
13	986753
14	2880595
15	8420967
16	24648441
17	72229449
18	211881339
19	622137483
20	1828359477
21	5377601112
22	15828541932
23	46622437134

Table 1: Some initial values of $\{\Delta b_n\}_{n \geq 0}$

Theorem 2. For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), $\{\Delta^3 A_n\}_{n \geq 2}$ is log-convex and $\{\Delta^3 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-balanced.

Proof. For convenience, let $b_n = \Delta^2 A_n$ ($n \geq 0$). It is clear that $\Delta^3 A_n = \Delta b_n$. It follows from (1) and (6) that

$$b_{n+1} = \frac{2(n+2)(2n+3)}{(n+3)(2n+1)}b_n + \frac{3(n-1)(2n+3)}{(n+3)(2n-1)}b_{n-1} \quad \text{for } n \geq 1. \tag{8}$$

Some initial values of $\{\Delta b_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ are given in Table 1. By using (8), we get

$$\Delta b_n = \left(1 + \frac{6}{2n^2 + 7n + 3}\right)b_n + \frac{3(2n+3)(n-1)}{(2n-1)(n+3)}b_{n-1}.$$

We find that $\{\Delta b_j\}_{2 \leq j \leq 23}$ is log-convex. In order to prove that the sequence $\{\Delta b_n\}_{n \geq 2}$ is log-convex, we need to show that $\{\Delta b_n\}_{n \geq 22}$ is log-convex. For $n \geq 1$,

let $g_n = \frac{(n-1)b_{n-1}}{n+3}$. We first prove that the sequence $\{g_n\}_{n \geq 22}$ is log-convex. For $n \geq 0$, put $x_n = \frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n}$ and $h_n = \frac{g_{n+1}}{g_n}$ ($n \geq 1$). It follows from (6) that

$$h_n = \frac{n(n+1)(n+3)(2n+1)}{(n-1)(n+2)(n+4)(2n-1)}x_{n-1}, \quad n \geq 1.$$

Due to (3), we obtain

$$\frac{h_{n+1}}{h_n} \geq \frac{4(n-1)(n+2)^2(n+4)^2(2n+3)(3n^2-1)}{3n(n+1)(n+3)^2(n+5)(2n-1)(2n+1)^2}.$$

Define

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_n &= 4(n-1)(n+2)^2(n+4)^2(2n+3)(3n^2-1) \\ &\quad - 3n(n+1)(n+3)^2(n+5)(2n-1)(2n+1)^2. \end{aligned}$$

By computation, we have

$$\Gamma_n = 10n^6 - 145n^5 - 1388n^4 - 3406n^3 - 2054n^2 + 1031n + 768 > 0 \quad (n \geq 22).$$

This implies that $\{h_n\}_{n \geq 22}$ is increasing, and hence $\{g_n\}_{n \geq 22}$ is log-convex. Note that $\{1 + \frac{6}{2n^2+7n+3}\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{b_n\}_{n \geq 3}$, and $\{\frac{2n+3}{2n-1}\}_{n \geq 1}$ are log-convex, and hence $\{\Delta b_n\}_{n \geq 22}$ is log-convex. For $n \geq 0$, let $y_n = \frac{b_{n+1}}{b_n}$ and $\bar{y}_n = \frac{\Delta b_{n+1}}{\Delta b_n}$. It follows from (8) that

$$\Delta b_{n+1} = \frac{6}{(n+4)(2n+3)} \cdot \Delta b_n + \left[\frac{3n(2n+5)}{(n+4)(2n+1)} + \frac{6}{(n+4)(2n+3)} \right] b_n. \quad (9)$$

By (9), we have

$$\frac{\bar{y}_n}{n+1} = \frac{6}{(n+1)(n+4)(2n+3)} + \frac{3n(2n+3)(2n+5) + 6(2n+1)}{(n+1)(n+4)(2n+1)(2n+3)(y_n-1)}.$$

We need to show that $\{\frac{\Delta b_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-concave. It suffices to prove that $\{\frac{\bar{y}_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is decreasing. Since the sequences $\{\frac{6}{(n+1)(n+4)(2n+3)}\}_{n \geq 2}$, $\{\frac{1}{y_n-1}\}_{n \geq 3}$, and $\{\frac{3n(2n+3)(2n+5)+6(2n+1)}{(n+1)(n+4)(2n+1)(2n+3)}\}_{n \geq 2}$ are decreasing, it follows that $\{\frac{\bar{y}_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is decreasing. Hence $\{\Delta b_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-balanced. \square

Theorem 3. For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), we have that $\{nA_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{\Delta(nA_n)\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{n \cdot \Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, and $\{n \cdot \Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ are log-concave.

Proof. For $n \geq 0$, let $x_n = \frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n}$. For $n \geq 1$, set $W_n = nA_n$, $s_n = \frac{W_{n+1}}{W_n}$, $t_n = \frac{W_{n+2}-W_{n+1}}{W_{n+1}-W_n}$, and $u_n = \frac{(n+1) \cdot \Delta A_{n+1}}{n \cdot \Delta A_n} = \frac{(n+1)(A_{n+2}-A_{n+1})}{n(A_{n+1}-A_n)}$. It is evident that

$$s_{n+1} - s_n = \frac{n(n+2)x_{n+1} - (n+1)^2x_n}{n(n+1)}, \quad t_n = \frac{s_n(s_{n+1}-1)}{s_n-1},$$

and

$$u_n = \frac{(n+1)x_n(x_{n+1}-1)}{n(x_n-1)}.$$

It follows from (4) and (5) that

$$\begin{aligned} n(n+2)x_{n+1} - (n+1)^2x_n &= n(n+2) \left[2 + \frac{3n}{(n+2)x_n} \right] - (n+1)^2x_n \\ &\leq n(n+2) \left[2 + \frac{3n}{(n+2)\mu_n} \right] - (n+1)^2\mu_n \\ &= -\frac{3n}{2(2n+1)} < 0 \quad (n \geq 1). \end{aligned}$$

This leads to $s_{n+1} - s_n < 0$ for $n \geq 1$, and hence the sequence $\{nA_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is log-concave. It follows from (1) that

$$W_{n+1} = \frac{2(n+1)}{n}W_n + 3W_{n-1} \quad \text{for } n \geq 2. \tag{10}$$

Applying (10), we have

$$s_n = \frac{2(n+1)}{n} + \frac{3}{s_{n-1}} \quad \text{for } n \geq 1.$$

Thus we obtain

$$t_n = \frac{s_n}{s_n-1} \left(\frac{n+3}{n+1} + \frac{3}{s_n} \right) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{s_n-1} \right) \frac{n+3}{n+1} + \frac{3}{s_n-1}.$$

It is obvious that $\{t_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is decreasing. Thus, $\{\Delta(nA_n)\}_{n \geq 1}$ is log-concave. Now we prove that the sequence $\{n \cdot \Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is log-concave. It follows from (4) that

$$u_n = \frac{n+1}{n} + \frac{n+1}{n(x_n-1)} + \frac{3(n+1)}{(n+2)(x_n-1)} \quad \text{for } n \geq 1. \tag{11}$$

By using (11), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} u_{n+1} - u_n &= -\frac{1}{n(n+1)} + \frac{n+2}{(n+1)(x_{n+1}-1)} + \frac{3(n+2)}{(n+3)(x_{n+1}-1)} - \frac{n+1}{n(x_n-1)} \\ &\quad - \frac{3(n+1)}{(n+2)(x_n-1)}. \end{aligned}$$

Noting that the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is increasing, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} u_{n+1} - u_n &\leq -\frac{1}{n(n+1)} + \frac{n+2}{(n+1)(x_n-1)} + \frac{3(n+2)}{(n+3)(x_n-1)} - \frac{n+1}{n(x_n-1)} \\ &\quad - \frac{3(n+1)}{(n+2)(x_n-1)} \\ &= \frac{3n(n+1) - (n+2)(n+3)x_n}{n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(x_n-1)}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows from (5) that

$$\begin{aligned} 3n(n+1) - (n+2)(n+3)x_n &\leq 3n(n+1) - (n+2)(n+3)\mu_n \\ &= -\frac{n(7n+11)}{2n+1} \quad (n \geq 1). \end{aligned}$$

This implies that $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is decreasing, and hence the sequence $\{n \cdot \Delta A_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is log-concave. It follows from (6) that $n \cdot \Delta^2 A_n = 2nA_n \cdot \frac{2n+1}{n+2}$. Since the two sequences $\{nA_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ and $\{\frac{2n+1}{n+2}\}_{n \geq 1}$ are both log-concave, it follows that $\{n \cdot \Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is also log-concave. \square

Theorem 4. *For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), $\{n^n A_n^n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is log-convex.*

Proof. For $n \geq 0$, put $x_n = \frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n}$ and $v_n = \frac{(n+1)^{n+1} A_{n+1}^{n+1}}{n^n A_n^n}$ ($n \geq 1$). It suffices to show that $\{v_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is increasing. It is obvious that

$$v_n = (n+1)A_{n+1} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n x_n^n.$$

Since the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-convex and $x_0 = 1$, it follows that $\{x_n^n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is increasing. On the other hand, the sequences $\{(1 + \frac{1}{n})^n\}_{n \geq 1}$ and $\{(n+1)A_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 1}$ are increasing. Thus, $\{v_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is increasing. \square

3. Concluding Remarks

For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), we have discussed the log-behavior of some sequences involving A_n . We mainly proved that $\{\Delta^2 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ and $\{\Delta^3 A_n\}_{n \geq 3}$ are log-balanced, where Δ is the (forward) difference operator. For $b_n = \Delta^2 A_n$, there is a conjecture (see sequence A026135 in the OEIS [9]) that states the following recurrence relation

$$(n+2)b_n - 3(n+1)b_{n-1} - (n+2)b_{n-2} + 3(n-3)b_{n-3} = 0 \quad \text{for } n \geq 3.$$

This conjecture holds as a consequence of (1) and (6). For $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, we now state a conjecture.

Conjecture 1. *For the sequence $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfying the recurrence relation (1), there exists a positive integer N such that $\{\Delta^4 A_n\}_{n \geq N}$ is log-convex.*

The author plans to study the various properties of $\{A_n\}_{n \geq 0}$.

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References

- [1] N. Asai, I. Kubo, and H.-H. Kuo, Bell numbers, log-concavity, and log-convexity, *Acta Appl. Math.* **63** (1–3) (2000), 79–87.
- [2] F. Brenti, Log-concave and unimodal sequences in algebra, combinatorics, and geometry: An update, *Contemp. Math.* **178** (1994), 71–89.
- [3] T. Došlić, Log-balanced combinatorial sequences, *Int. J. Math. Math. Sci.* **4** (2005), 507–522.
- [4] T. Došlić, Seven (lattice) paths to log-convexity, *Acta Appl. Math.* **110** (3) (2010), 1373–1392.
- [5] T. Došlić, D. Svrtan, and D. Veljan, Enumerative aspects of secondary structures, *Discrete Math.* **285** (1–3) (2004), 67–82.
- [6] T. Došlić and D. Veljan, Logarithmic behavior of some combinatorial sequences, *Discrete Math.* **308** (11) (2008), 2182–2212.
- [7] L.L. Liu and Y. Wang, On the log-convexity of combinatorial sequences, *Adv. in Appl. Math.* **39** (4) (2007), 453–476.
- [8] O. Milenkovic and K.J. Compton, Probabilistic transforms for combinatorial urn models, *Combin. Probab. Comput.* **13** (4–5) (2004), 645–675.
- [9] OEIS Foundation Inc., The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, <https://oeis.org>.
- [10] R.P. Stanley, *Log-concave and unimodal sequences in algebra, combinatorics, and geometry*, Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences, **576** (1989), 500–535.
- [11] R.P. Stanley, *Enumerative Combinatorics, Vol. 2*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1999.
- [12] F.-Z. Zhao, On the log-convexity of the difference sequence of a log-convex sequence, *Sarajevo J. of Math.* **16** (2) (2020), 153–162.